

#EUSTEELInTime

Zhyron

Funded by
the European Union

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**Against
all wars**

1951

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**More
cooperation
equals more
strength**

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Against all wars

An alliance made
of Steel and Coal

1951

1957

1970

1977

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The famine in Germany after the war.
The sign says "We want coal, we want food".

In the aftermath of World War II, Europe lays in ruins

economically,
physically,
and **psychologically.**

Determined to prevent another devastating conflict, six nations (**France, West Germany, Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands, and Luxembourg**) sought a fresh approach to international cooperation.

The map of the ECSC founding members

On **May 9, 1950**, at 4 PM, French Foreign Minister **Robert Schuman** delivered a historic speech proposing a unified Europe through economic and political cooperation.

Robert Schuman during his historical speech.

○ Signing the Treaty of Paris (1951).

Known as the **Schuman Declaration**, it laid the foundation for European integration, leading to the **Treaty of Paris (April 18, 1951)** that creates the **European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC)** the first step towards the European Union.

By **unifying the coal and steel industries**, the signatory countries hoped to make **future wars not only undesirable but practically impossible**, since coal and steel were essential for armament production. This common market also aimed to spur growth through shared resources and a dismantling of trade barriers.

The first "European ingots", produced during a dedicated event to celebrate the newly signed Treaty of Paris.

Although initially limited to two commodities, **the ECSC became the launch pad for broader European collaboration**, setting a precedent for managing critical industries through supranational institutions.

It was a **bold statement** that European nations could move beyond historical enmities, pooling sovereignty for mutual benefit and stability.

The Ruhr region in Germany during the 50s.

**More
cooperation
equals more
strength**

The age of prosperity

The Signing of the Treaty of Rome (1957).

Just six years after establishing the ECSC, the same six countries (**France, West Germany, Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands, and Luxembourg**) reconvened to build on that momentum. On **March 25, 1957**, they signed the **Treaties of Rome**, which established the **European Economic Community (EEC)** and **Euratom**.

This new step broadened their shared vision, shifting from a narrow focus on coal and steel to a **more comprehensive economic integration** across different sectors.

The EEC introduced the foundational “**four freedoms**”, the free movement of goods, services, people, and capital, and laid down the principles for a customs union among member states.

While the ECSC persisted as a distinct legal entity, it was increasingly seen as **part of the wider European project**.

An Italian poster celebrating the Treaty of Rome. The poster says: “United Europe for the progress and peace” (top); “Signing of the Treaties for the common market and EURATOM”

The steel sector, in particular, **benefited from coordinated approaches to production and trade under** the EEC framework, basically by the removal of internal barriers (that eliminates tariffs and quotas on trade between the six countries) and by adopting a common external tariff (steelmakers could compete more effectively without facing unequal protectionist policies among member states).

○ ECSC production in ingots (1957-2000)

Steel in turmoil

Europe's industry
struggles and reforms

1951

1957

1970

1977

2002

2019

2030

Throughout the 1970s and 1980s, while new members were joining the European Communities, Europe's steel industry fell into a state of upheaval: several forces converged to trigger this crisis.

○ European enlargement process (1951-2013)

Overproduction led to excess steel supply, undercutting prices and profitability. Meanwhile, **new global competitors** brought modern facilities and lower labour costs, intensifying **international competition**.

○ Percentage share of raw steel produced by US, EC, Japan and the rest of the world

In parallel,
demand for steel began
to weaken at home, partly due
to **economic restructuring** and
the rise of **alternative materials**.

A **general crisis** based on
the rise of oil price followed
through all the continental
economy.

○ Employment in the steel industry in the EC and US

These pressures prompted grave concerns about job losses and the economic vitality of steel-dependent regions. In response, **the European Economic Community introduced restructuring measures**, which involved **scaling back production capacity and offering subsidies** to facilitate industrial conversion.

Although the period was painful,
with the closure of factories and the need
for communities to move forward new
economic activities, **it forced
the industry to modernize.**

Ultimately, Europe's steel producers embarked on a path to **become more efficient, innovative, and competitive** in a rapidly changing world.

This was mostly due to a turning point in the industrial history of Europe: **the Davignon Plan.**

The Cure

The Davignon Plan

1951

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At the end of the 1970s,
**Europe was experiencing
a harsh climate of economic
and social turmoil.**

The oil crisis, widespread
unemployment,
and general unrest did not
spare the steel industry,
which had already lost
the momentum it had
enjoyed at the beginning
of the decade.

During those years, the **European Commissioner for Industry was the Belgian Etienne Davignon.**

Coming from an old and distinguished family that had served in Belgian diplomacy for over a century, Davignon was a pragmatic and direct man of industry.

Visit of Etienne Davignon, Vice-President of the CEC, to the JRC in Ispra

Launched in **1977**,
his policy framework,
named the **Davignon Plan**,
was aimed at stabilizing
a market plagued by overcapacity
and fierce global competition

at any price.

The Plan introduced a range of coordinated measures, **including production quotas** to prevent further market saturation, export restrictions to curb trade imbalances, and **financial incentives** for companies to close or modernize uncompetitive plants.

Though these steps were **sometimes controversial**, particularly among workers facing redundancy, they formed **one of the earliest examples of a unified industrial policy at the European level**.

By acting collectively, member states hoped to share both the burdens and benefits of reform.

In the long run,
the plan not only saved parts
of Europe's steel industry but also
**provided a prototype for
addressing common economic
challenges** through collaborative
governance.

By the 1990s, **privatization and technological advancements helped the industry regain some strength**, though globalization continued to pose challenges. The shift toward high-value steel products and increased automation marked a **new phase** for European steelmakers.

The Union

ECSC integration
into EU Treaties

1951

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The Treaty of Paris, signed in 1951, established the European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC) for 50 years. **On July 23, 2002, the treaty expired, and the ECSC was formally dissolved**, with its functions integrated into the broader EU framework.

Lowering the flag of the ECSC.

More than a legal transition, this marked the absorption of the ECSC's mission **promoting unity and prosperity through shared industrial management** into the expanding European project. Though the ECSC ended, its legacy continued in the EU's efforts to **manage strategic sectors** and **foster cross-border cooperation.**

Following the industrial crisis of the 1980s, **Europe's iron industry began reshaping itself** toward greater sustainability and innovation. Between 2000 and 2020, it faced growing global competition, driving modernization and consolidation.

Berlaymont Palace - Seat of the European Commission.

At the same time, tightening EU environmental regulations spurred the adoption of cleaner technologies. By the late 2010s, the industry was increasingly aligned with the EU's climate ambitions, investing in decarbonization and circular economy practices under the **European Green Deal**.

The Green Deal has become the fertile ground from which forward-looking initiatives like the **ZHyRON project** have emerged.

A bold vision for a cleaner, more resilient industrial future.

Frans Timmermans, at the podium.

Commitment to the future

The European Green Deal

In today's globalized and climate-conscious world, the **European Union** remains at the forefront of shaping the steel sector's future.

Central to this is
the **European Green Deal**,
an ambitious plan to make Europe
climate-neutral by 2050.
The plan was presented in 2019.

The Green Deal sets clear expectations:

reducing greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% in 2030, **achieving full climate neutrality** by mid-century, and **transitioning to a circular, sustainable industrial model**. For the steel industry, this means a profound transformation in how steel is produced, recycled, and integrated into the European economy.

A key point in this transformation is the shift away from traditional blast furnaces powered by coal, towards low-carbon technologies such as electric arc furnaces and hydrogen-based direct reduction.

Moreover, the Green Deal emphasizes circularity and resource efficiency. In the context of steel, this means greater emphasis on **green production**, improved **recycling of by-products**, and innovations that allow for **materials recovery**. Approaches that reduce environmental impact while supporting industrial competitiveness.

Although high energy prices, global market pressure, and the need for massive investment in new infrastructure keep challenging the industry, the Green Deal provides a **policy framework** that positions the European steel industry not just to survive the green transition but **to lead it.**

Green and Clean

The future of the
European steel industry

The European steel industry stands at a **pivotal crossroads**. Faced with global competition, high energy costs, and the urgent need to decarbonise, its future depends on the successful integration of innovation and sustainability.

In response to these challenges, the European Commission introduced the **Clean Industrial Deal** in early 2025 as part of its broader competitiveness strategy.

This initiative aims to transform **decarbonisation from a cost burden into a growth opportunity by mobilising over €100 billion** to support clean technologies. For sectors like steel, which are both energy-intensive and essential to Europe's industrial base, this deal represents a major shift towards **long-term resilience and green transformation.**

Among the projects that naturally embody the goals of the Clean Industrial Deal features **ZHyRON, an EU-funded research initiative** focused on steelmaking by-products started in 2024. ZHyRON addresses one of the most pressing issues in the steel sector: **how to reduce waste and emissions while recovering valuable materials.**

The project proposes innovative solutions by **developing a process that uses green hydrogen to treat iron-rich and zinc-containing by-products from steel production.** In doing so, the project supports the dual objectives of sustainability and competitiveness laid out in the EU's industrial strategy and the Green Deal.

This new phase
in European industrial policy
builds on a deep-rooted tradition
of **cross-border cooperation**
and **innovation in heavy industry**.

The journey began in 1951 with the creation of the **European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC)**, which laid the groundwork for European integration by uniting key industries. After a harsh period, and thanks to the common industrial initiatives, in 2019 the **European Green Deal** raised the bar, setting an ambitious path toward climate neutrality by 2050.

Oxycutting at the exit of the continuous casting at the steel mill of Serémange, France

Now, the **Clean Industrial Deal** represents the latest evolution in this trajectory—one that seeks to reconcile economic competitiveness with climate goals, ensuring that European industry, and steel in particular, remains **strong, sustainable, and globally relevant**. In this broader transformation, ZHyRON is set to play its part.

Timmermans delivering a speech about the Green Deal at the European Investment Bank Headquarters, Caroline Martin

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